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Communication Strategies in Raising Awareness Public Awareness of Toddler Immunization

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Abstract

Communication strategy is planning (planning) and management (management) to achieve a goal. However, to achieve these goals, it does not function as a road map that only shows the direction, but must be able to show how the operational tactics. The purpose of this study was to determine the communication strategy, the level of public awareness and immunization of toddlers. This research uses descriptive qualitative methods, sampling techniques using purposive techniques. Data collection is done by conducting interviews. The sampling technique uses non-random sampling consisting of people who have toddlers, public health center, Immunization Coordinator, Village Midwife, and Cadres. Based on the results of the study found that the immunization communication strategy is carried out by conducting counseling to the community using media such as brochures, posters, effective communication using language that is easy to understand. To increase immunization coverage, it is necessary to search for toddlers who have not been immunized at home. Increased public awareness in immunization is seen from the number of immunization coverage reports, immunization book guidelines and monthly report results and there are still some people who have not immunized their toddlers because there is no permission from their husbands, where husbands forbid immunization of their children, for fear that their children will have a fever and the issue of fake vaccines that make parents do not want to immunize their toddlers.

Keyword: Communication Strategy; Public Awareness Level; Toddler Immunization

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INTRODUCTION

Communication strategy is planning (planning) and management (management) to achieve a goal. However, to achieve this goal, it does not function as a road map that only shows the direction but must be able to show how the operational tactics. A strategy is one of the steps planned to achieve a goal by using certain message activities and media (Effendy Onong Uchjana, 2005).

Therefore, a special body is needed to accommodate ideas that can help develop the strategy. One of the most important steps is to establish a "communication strategy". A good communication strategy is a strategy that can establish or place one's position appropriately in communication with the opposite communication to achieve the communication goals that have been set. In a communication strategy understanding a strategy is not enough, it requires a level of awareness from the community so that it is easy for the community to understand a communication strategy used.

The development of communication continues to follow the improvement of the quality of human thinking. The communication process is no longer in the stage of describing feelings that revolve around a small and limited scope but has led humans to be oriented towards a wider and more complex scale. How important is the role and function of communication that is always side by side with humans in all fields of life, so that it begins to feel the need for wise and patterned management of all aspects of communication (Hikmat & Mahi, 2014).

The World Health Organization (WHO) and UNICEF launched the Global Immunization Vision and Strategy (GIVS), a 10-year action plan to prevent avoidable diseases through immunization. The goal of GIVS until 2010 is to increase country immunization coverage to at least 90% of national immunization coverage and at least 80% of immunization coverage in each district or administrative area to determine the equitable distribution of immunization to all children. In addition, the National Immunization Acceleration Movement (GAIN-UCI) immunization program was launched in 2010 to achieve 100% Universal Child Immunization (UCI) in villages by 2014, which means that 100% of villages in Indonesia have reached the UCI stage, i.e. 80% or more of infants up to 1 year of age in the village have received complete basic immunization (Kemenkes, 2009).

The three provinces with the highest achievement of complete basic immunization in infants in 2015 were Jambi (99.85%), West Nusa Tenggara (99.32%), and Lampung (99.22%). The three provinces with the lowest achievements were Papua (47.27%), followed by West Papua (57.11%), and Central Kalimantan (64.86%) (Profil Kesehatan Indonesia, 2015). Based on the immunization coverage achieved by NAD province for BCG 75.5%, Polio 65.9%, DPT 58.0%, HB 3 54.2% and measles 71.4%. BCG immunization coverage was highest in Banda Aceh at 93.1% and lowest in Gayo Lues (10.2%). Polio 3 and DPT 3 immunizations were highest in Aceh Tengah at 87.9% and 92.4% respectively and lowest in Gayo Lues for Polio 3 (17.0%) and DPT 3 (4.7%) respectively. HB 3 immunization was highest in Bener Meriah (86.8%) lowest in Gayo Lues (2.3%) and measles immunization was highest in Sabang 95.0% and lowest in Gayo Lues (2.3%) (Riset Kesehatan Dasar, 2007).

The communication strategy carried out by the Puskesmas of Manggeng Sub-district in increasing public awareness of immunization of toddlers is by reaching out to the community/family by forming a team from the Puskesmas in collaboration with the local village midwife. The team fosters housewives and is also tasked with recording how many mothers are pregnant, nursing mothers, toddlers, sick people and so on.

One of the obstacles in increasing immunization coverage is due to the perception of the Manggeng community on the issue of fake vaccines and the absence of support from parents so that they do not allow their children to be immunized on the grounds that their children will have a fever. This is related to the lack of parental knowledge of the importance of immunization. This is in line with the research of Luthy et al., (2009) in Utah, United States that the delay in immunization is due to several things, one of which is that they want their children to get immunized at an older age.²⁰ Another study also revealed that 13 - 40% of parents refused and delayed immunization of their children due to parental concerns about immunization in early childhood (Dempsey et al., 2011).

Based on the description above; to gain public trust, the Puskesmas of Manggeng Sub-district must always improve a better communication strategy in providing understanding and awareness to the community of the importance of immunization for toddlers. Departing from the above problems, the problem formulations used in the following research are: 1. How is the communication strategy of the manggeng health center in increasing public awareness of immunization in toddlers? 2. What is the level of public awareness of immunization in toddlers? Based on the formulation of the problem above, the objectives of this study are as follows: 1. To find out the communication strategy of the manggeng health center in increasing public awareness of immunization of toddlers. increasing public awareness of immunization in toddlers 2. To determine the level of public awareness of manggeng towards immunization in toddlers.

METHOD

This research was conducted at the Puskesmas of Manggeng District, Southwest Aceh Regency. Given the wide range of work of the Manggeng Health Center, the authors limit the research which only focuses on communication strategies in increasing public awareness of immunization of toddlers. This research uses descriptive qualitative approaches and methods. This qualitative research is research that can explain and analyze phenomena, events, social activities, attitudes beliefs, perceptions of a person or group towards something (Hamdi Asep Saepul, & Baharuddin, 2014). Descriptive means that data is collected in the form of words, pictures and not numbers, all data collected is likely to be the key to what has been studied.⁷⁹ This research prioritizes direct data, so that the researchers themselves go to the field to conduct observations and interviews (Hamdi Asep Saepul, & Baharuddin, 2014).

FINDING AND DISCUSSION

The effective communication strategy used by the Manggeng Health Center for immunization of toddlers goes through 4 stages, namely: a. Data finding (Collecting Data) Searching for data and collecting facts and data before someone carries out communication activities. To speak in front of the public, it is necessary to find facts and data about the community's desires, composition and so on. Based on the results of the study, it shows that data collection carried out by the Manggeng puskesmas is carried out in two ways, the first way is done by visiting the homes of people who have children under five and the second way is done at the puskesmas, this is as stated by the head of the puskesmas below. "The data collection process is carried out at home and at the health center, data collection is carried out by visiting the homes of people

who have children under five and asking their names, ages, weighing and measuring height and as. And data collection at the health center is carried out when the mother gives birth at the health center. Recording the data is carried out in the immunization report book that is already available". Then the immunization coordinator also said that the data collection process was carried out on mothers who gave birth at the puskesmas. "The data collection process carried out at the health center is carried out on mothers who give birth at the health center at that time. The data collection process is carried out after the baby is born and the first immunization is immediately given to the baby".

b. Planning, from facts and data, a plan is made about what to say and how to say it. Until this process, planning is carried out. based on research, there are 2 ways of planning. the first way is to provide direction and the second way is to communicate interpersonally. This is as stated by the head of the puskesmas below. "The communication strategy plan carried out by the manggeng health center will first be given direction or guidance such as training given to health workers and cadres before counseling. After being given guidance or direction, interpersonal communication is carried out. " In addition, the immunization coordinator said that the direction or guidance that will be given is in the form of training, after being given new training, counseling is carried out to the community. "First given direction or guidance, usually given in the form of training, after the training is given new counseling to the community".

c. Communicating After planning has been prepared, the next step is to communicate. There are two forms of communication carried out, the first is done by counseling. This is as stated by the immunization coordinator below. "Communication is used by counseling the community and the counseling itself will be given directly by the puskesmas". Then the second communication uses the media, the media used is in the form of brochures, posters and leaflets. This is as expressed by one of the village midwives below. "Effective communication is used for mothers who have toddlers, namely by using language that is easily understood by these mothers. The media used in the counseling is using leaflets, posters, brochures. The stages of communication carried out by the puskesmas by looking at the right situation and time so that the communication provided is effective. This is as stated by the immunization coordinator below. "The manggeng health center conducts counseling and distributes media such as leaflets, posters and brochures to the community during the harvest season. "As stated by the head of the manggeng health center, where the media used in communication is very important for the community. Support the message or information conveyed to the community through counseling so that the community understands and understands the message or information conveyed by the Manggeng puskesmas. In addition, communication is also carried out interpersonally by counseling the homes of people who have toddlers. This is as stated by the village midwife below. "Communication is also carried out interpersonally with the community by conducting counseling at the homes of people who have toddlers to conduct socialization about immunization for people who do not have time to come to the posyandu and people who are still closed about this immunization".

d. Evaluation (Evaluation) Assessment and re-analyzing for each time, the results of the communication. This is needed to be used as material for further planning. Based on the results of the research, the Manggeng Health Center considers that the communication strategy carried out so far has been quite effective in accordance with the message or information provided to

the community. This is as stated by the immunization coordinator below. "So far the communication strategy has been successful and quite effective in accordance with the delivery of messages or information to the community. The community is also starting to accept, although some are afraid of the rampant issue of fake vaccines". However, the Manggeng puskesmas also still needs to make improvements to make it even better considering the phenomenon of the rampant issue of fake vaccines circulating and unsettling among the community. This is as stated by the village midwife below. "Currently, the community has understood the message conveyed by the puskesmas, although there are still those who are afraid of immunizing their toddlers due to the rampant issue of fake vaccines circulating and the issue of vaccines containing pork". The side effects of using the vaccine are also conveyed when the manggeng puskesmas conveys messages or information to the community. This is as stated by the cadre below. "Cadres also assist the village midwife in conveying information to neighbors and the community. The cadre also said that information obtained by the community from messages or information if immunization is given to children will cause fever, making parents afraid to immunize their children".

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the above research, it can be concluded that the effective communication strategy carried out by the Manggeng Community Health Center is by carrying out four stages, namely collecting data, planning, communicating, and evaluating. The current strategy is carried out by providing counseling to the community using media such as brochures, posters, leaflet, conducting effective communication using language that is easy to understand, and the last step taken is to search for toddlers who have not been immunized at home. Increased public awareness in immunization is seen from the immunization adequacy rate, immunization adequacy reports, immunization book guidelines and monthly report results and there are still some people who have not immunized their toddlers because there is no permission from their husbands, where husbands forbid immunization of their children, for fear that their children will have a fever and the issue of fake vaccines that make parents do not want to immunize their toddlers.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Ahmadi UF. (2006). *Imunisasi Mengapa Perlu*. Jakarta: Kompas Media Sarana.
- Alamsyah Dedi. (2012). *Manajemen Pelayanan Kesehatan*. Yogyakarta: Nuha Medika.
- Anggraini, Sutomo. (2010). *Menu Sehat Alami Untuk Batita dan Balita*. Jakarta: Demedia.
- Ardianto, Lukiati Komala, Karlinah Siti. (2007). *Komunikasi Massa Suatu Pengantar*. Bandung: Simbiosis Rekatam Media.
- Basrowi, Suwandi. (2009). *Memahami Penelitian Kualitatif*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- Bungin Burhan. (2004). *Analisis Data Penelitian Kualitatif*. Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Persada.
- Cahyono, S, B. (2010). *Vaksinasi Cara Ampuh Cegah Penyakit Infeksi*. Yogyakarta: Kanisius.

- Cangara Hafied. (2013). *Perencanaan dan Strategi Komunikasi*. Jakarta: RajaGrafindo.
- Dempsey, A.D & Dempsey, A.P., Widyastuti, Palupi, Adiningsih, Dian. (2011). *Riset keperawatan*. Jakarta: EGC.
- Dewi Vivian Nanny Lia. (2013). *Asuhan Neonatus Bayi dan Anak Balita*. Jakarta: Salemba Medika.
- Dinkes. (2005). *Dinas Kesehatan*. Jakarta: Dinkes.
- Dwiendra Octa, Maita Liva., Saputri Eka Maya., dan Yulviana Rina. (2014). *Asuhan Kebidanan Neonatus, Bayi/Balita dan Anak Prasekolah untuk Para Bidan*. Yogyakarta: Budi Utama.
- Effendy, Onong Uchjan. (2004). *Dinamika Komunikasi*. Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarya.
- Effendy, Onong Uchjan. (2005). *Ilmu Komunikasi Teori dan Pratek*. Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarya.
- Geller, E.S. (2000). *Behavioral Safety Analysis. A Necessary Precorsor To Correction Action Professional Safety*.
- Griffin Ricky W. (2004). *Manajemen*. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- Gunawan, Imam. (2014). *Metode Penelitian Kualitatif: Teori dan Praktik*. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara.
- Hadijono Harun Sari. (1980). *Sejarah Filsafat Barat 2*. Yogyakarta: Kanisius.
- Hamdi Asep Saepul, Baharuddin E. (2014). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif Aplikasi Dalam Pendidikan*. Yogyakarta: Budi Utama.
- Harnilawati. (2013). *Konsep dan Proses Keperawatan Keluarga*. Sulawesi Selatan: Pustaka as Salam.
- Puskesmas. (2016). *Hasil Data Dokumentasi dan Laporan*. Puskesmas Kecamatan Manggeng.
- Heru Adi. (1995). *Kader Kesehatan Masyarakat*. Jakarta: EGC.
- Hidayat A Aziz Alimul. (2008). *Pengantar Ilmu Kesehatan Anak untuk Pendidikan Kebidanan*. Jakarta: Salemba Medika.
- Hikmat, mahi. (2014). *Metode Penelitian; Dalam Perspektif Ilmu Komunikasi*. Yogyakarta: Graha Ilmu.
- Iqbal Mubarak Wahit, Chayatin Nurul., Rozikin Khoirul., dan Supradi. (2007). *Promosi Kesehatan*. Yogyakarta: Graha Ilmu.
- Kemenkes. (2009). *Profil Kesehatan Indonesia*. Jakarta: Kemenkes RI.
- Komala, lukiati. (2009). *Komunikasi Masssa*. Jakarta: Simbiosis Rekatama Media.
- Kriyantono Rachmat. (2008). *Teknik Praktis Riset Komunikasi*. Jakarta: Kecana.
- Marimbi, H. *Tumbuh Kembang, Status Gizi dan Imunisasi Dasar Pada Balita*. Yogyakarta: Nuha Medika, 2010.